

Mixed Ligand Complexes of Manganese-, Cobalt-, Nickel- and Zinc-(II) with *o*-Vanillin and 4,6-Dihydroxypyrimidine in Ethanol – Water (70%) Media

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Stability constants of mixed-ligand complexes of Mn^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} with *o*-vanillin and 4,6-dihydroxypyrimidine (70% ethanol-water media) were calculated from polarographic data using Schaap and McMasters' method. For the Mn^{II} mixed-ligand complex, Crow's mean diffusion coefficient method was also used and the results compared well with that from the former method. Mixing, stabilisation and disproportionation constants for the mixed-ligand complexes have also been reported.

POLAROGRAPHY is being more widely used in complexometry of mixed ligand complexes, which aims at probing the competitive behaviour of pairs of biologically active ligands¹ for complexation with a metal ion. However, irreversible nature of most of the polarographic waves, especially for single ligand complexes, prevents its application for obtaining values of stability constants of 1 : 1 complexes of most cations. Crow² applied the decrease in limiting current of a cation on complexation with a ligand for obtaining formation curves of complexes. This method can be used universally for both reversible and irreversible polarographic waves. In the present communication we have reported the stabilities of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} - 1 : 1 : 1 complexes with *o*-vanillin and 4,6-dihydroxypyrimidine using Schaap and McMasters' method³ for the waves with slopes of about 30 mV. Mn^{II} waves had slopes of 30–50 mV with increasing concentrations of the two ligands and hence Crow's method was also applied and the stability was found to be marginally different from that calculated by the former method.

Experimental

o-Vanillin (Ega Chemie, West Germany) and 4,6-dihydroxypyrimidine (Aldrich, U.S.A.) were used as complexing agents.

A test solution contained metal ion (1.0 mmol dm^{-3}), *o*-vanillin (0.1 M), $LiClO_4$ (0.1 mol dm^{-3}), gelatin (0.005%) and ethanol (70 volume percent in water) and increasing amounts of 4,6-dihydroxypyrimidine (0–0.005 mol dm^{-3}).

An ELICO LI-120 digital pH-meter, a Polariter PO4g Radiometer polarograph (chart speed 2 cm min^{-1}), a Julabo F-40 HC (West Germany) circulating thermostat and Sargent capillary with $m=1.068$ mg s^{-1} and $t=4.3$ s for 70 cm Hg head in aqueous

$LiClO_4$ (0.1 mol dm^{-3}) at zero potential (SCE) and double-walled Kalousek cell were used. Temperature was maintained at 298 ± 0.02 K.

Results and Discussion

Binary systems: The stepwise formation constants of the complexes of Mn^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} with *o*-vanillin and 4,6-dihydroxypyrimidine were determined separately⁴ under identical conditions before the studies on mixed ligand systems were taken up. The results are summarised in Table 1.

TABLE 1—FORMATION CONSTANTS OF BINARY COMPLEXES

Ligand	Mn^{II}	Co^{II}	Ni^{II}	Zn^{II}
<i>o</i> -Vanillin	6.67	8.04	7.78	7.79
4,6-Dihydroxypyrimidine	7.73	8.89	9.29	10.21

Mixed systems: The metal-*o*-VAN-4,6-DHP systems were studied by keeping the concentration of the weaker ligand (*o*-VAN) constant and varying the concentration of the other ligand. In all the systems single well-defined polarographic waves were obtained which exhibited negative $E_{1/2}$ shifts with increasing 4,6-dihydroxypyrimidine concentration.

The data for overall stability constants $\beta_{1,1}$ calculated by the method of Schaap and McMasters³ are given in Table 2 and the results summarised in Table 3.

The tendency for addition of *o*-vanillin to $M(4,6-DHP)$ and $M(o-VAN)$ systems are given by the respective $\log K$ values : (1.77, 2.67) and (2.08, 2.67) (Crow's), (5.91, 3.34), (5.18, 2.33) and (6.18, 3.41) for Mn^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} ions. The differences are much larger than the statistical value of 0.3 indicating greater stabilisation. Due to the

TABLE 2—DATA FOR CATION-*o*-VANILLIN-4,6-DIHYDROXYPYRIMIDINE COMPLEXES
 [Metal ion]=1.0 mmol dm⁻³, [LiClO₄]=0.1 mmol dm⁻³, [*o*-vanillin]=0.1 mol dm⁻³, Temp.=298 K

Cation	Concentration of 4,6-dihydroxypyrimidine (mol dm ⁻³)							
	0.00000	0.00001	0.00005	0.00010	0.00050	0.0010	0.0020	0.0050
Mn ^{II} pH=7.7								
<i>E</i> _{1/2}	1.33	1.37	1.39	1.40	1.42	1.43	1.45	1.47
<i>I</i> _d	1.72	1.61	1.59	1.58	1.56	1.55	1.54	1.53
(Schaap and McMasters') (Crow's)	log A=1.20 log K _{1}=5.30}		log B=6.25 log K _{2}=6.25}			log C=9.24 log β _{2}=11.55}		
Co ^{II} pH=8.0								
<i>E</i> _{1/2}	1.29	1.45	1.48	1.50	1.53	1.55	1.56	1.59
<i>I</i> _d	2.44	2.32	2.29	2.28	2.27	2.26	2.24	2.22
	log A=5.90		log B=9.69			log C=14.74		
Ni ^{II} pH=7.0								
<i>E</i> _{1/2}	1.12	1.26	1.28	1.29	1.32	1.34	1.35	1.37
<i>I</i> _d	3.97	3.72	3.68	3.64	3.60	3.58	3.57	3.55
	log A=4.60		log B=9.57			log C=13.07		
Zn ^{II} pH=6.2								
<i>E</i> _{1/2}	1.20	1.38	1.40	1.41	1.45	1.46	1.48	1.51
<i>I</i> _d	2.71	2.56	2.53	2.51	2.50	2.48	2.47	2.46
	log A=5.76		log B=10.47			log C=14.96		

A, B and C refer to the coefficients of the F₀₀ [X, Y] function of Schaap and McMasters, F₀₀ [X, Y]=A+B[X]+C[X]²+...

TABLE 3—STABILITY CONSTANTS (log β₁₁), DISPROPORTIONATION CONSTANTS (log X), Δlog K, MIXING CONSTANT (log K_M) AND STABILISATION CONSTANT (log K_s) FOR MIXED-LIGAND COMPLEXES OF M(II)

Metal	log β ₁₁ (expt.)	log X ^a	Δlog K ^b	log K _M ^c	log K _s ^d
Mn ^{II}	7.25, 7.56 ^e (7.59 ^f)	0.02 (0.59 ^e)	-2.23 (-1.92 ^e)	0.04	0.34
Co ^{II}	10.69 (9.76 ^f)	4.45	1.23	2.23	2.58
Ni ^{II}	10.57 (8.96 ^f)	3.83	-0.20	1.92	2.22
Zn ^{II}	11.47 (9.42 ^f)	4.74	1.70	2.37	2.67

^alog X=2 log β_{MAB}^M - (log β_{MA₂}^M + log β_{MB₂}^M). ^bΔlog K=log K_{MA}^{MAB} - log K_M^{MB}. ^clog K_M=log β₁₁ - ½(log β₂₀ + log β₀₂).
^dlog K_s=log K_M + log 2. ^eFrom Crow's method. ^fβ₁₁ (statistical)=log (2 × β₂₀^{1/2} × β₀₂^{1/2}).

quasi-reversible nature of the waves for the Mn^{II}-1:1:1 complex, Crow's method² is apparently more suitable for computation of the stability constant.

The logarithms of the disproportionation constants⁶, log X (Table 3) are much higher than the statistical value of 0.6 unit for Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} ternary complexes and 0.54 unit for Mn^{II} complex (Crow's method), indicating that mixed complexes are preferred over the binary complexes.

The values of Δlog K (K_{MA}^{MAB} - K_M^{MB}) (Table 3) show that it has a large negative value for the Mn^{II} complexes and a small negative value for Ni^{II} complexes as expected statistically. However, positive values of the Co^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes indicate that the disproportionation reaction (MA+MB⇌MAB+M) is more on the right side. Such observations have also been reported by Sahai

et al.⁶ for Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} who suggested that this might be due to neutralisation of charge.

The preferential formation of the ternary complexes are also seen from the values of mixing and stabilisation constants⁷ as given in Table 3.

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